

Interpolation of high-frequency radar velocities

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Summary

The main goal of this work is to present the design and the implementation of a procedure for the reconstruction of surface velocity fields in different coastal regions of Europe, by applying an advanced spatio-temporal interpolation technique on high-frequency radar (HFR) radial velocities.

Such velocity fields are particularly relevant in several applications, among which: oil and pollution spill detection (Abascal et al., 2009; Bellomo et al., 2015), search and rescue activities, ports and harbors management, storm surge and flooding. It can also be used for data assimilation purposes in numerical forecast models.

The measurement of sea surface velocities using high-frequency radar is now a mature technique, including in the European seas (Rubio et al., 2017). As of July 2021, there are 107 HF radars in Europe, for a total of 69 ongoing systems, according to the EuroGOOS HF Radar Task Team (<https://eurogoos.eu/high-frequency-radar-task-team/>).

For the sake of conciseness, most of the document focuses on the Gulf of Manfredonia, even if several other regions were addressed and gridded field created. The choice of this regions comes from the availability of four antenna sites, allowing us to perform cross-validation by discarding one of the sites.

As final results, we provide the gridded field as netCDF files following the Climate and Forecast (CF) conventions and the recommendation of the EuroGOOS HFR Task Team.

1 Data: radial velocities

1.1 Data access

The data files processed in this work were accessed through a THREDDS Data Server (TDS) provided by the EMODnet Physics colleagues. The data reading was performed using the OPeNDAP protocol, so the files were never downloaded locally. This also means that if the interpolation is performed on a super-computer, users need to ensure that the nodes are connected to the internet.

The Copernicus Marine Environment and Monitoring Service (CMEMS) also provides radar radial velocities under the product "Global Ocean-Delayed Mode in-situ Observations of surface (drifters and HFR) and sub-surface (vessel-mounted ADCPs) water velocity" (INSITU_GLO_UV_L2_REP_OBSERVATIONS_013_044, doi:10.48670/moi-00040).

Since this product was also available via the same THREDDS server, we applied the same interpolation procedure to them (see Section 5 in particular).

1.2 Spatial coverage of HFR systems

Each antenna site that constitutes a HFR system provides measurements of surface current velocities on concentric circles, as shown in Fig. 1 (one point on the map means one location of measurements). However at a given time, the coverage is rarely complete and many locations are not assigned a radial velocity (Fig. 2).

Figure 1 | Spatial structure of the measurements provided by a unique HFR site.

When combining all the available sites of a given system, one can obtain a coverage similar to that of Fig. 3: the central part of the domain is characterized by velocities measured by four sites, while the northernmost part of the domain has velocities only from one site.

1.3 Regions of interest

Numerous domains are covered by HFR systems in Europe, most of them are available via the THREDDS server. In this report we will focus on the following regions, while others can be progressively added:

- The Gulf of Manfredonia, on the Adriatic coast of Italy.
- The Gulf of Trieste, in the northern Adriatic Sea.

Figure 2 | Radial velocities for a single station on May 15, 2015 at 6 pm.

Figure 3 | Radial velocities for the 4 sites of the Gulf of Manfredonia.

- The Gulf of Naples, along the western coast of Italy.
- The northeast of Gran Canaria, in the Atlantic Ocean.

The Gulf of Manfredonia is of particular interest, thanks to the availability of up to 4 sites providing radial velocities. Details about the implementation of this HFR system can be found in [Corgnati et al. \(2019\)](#). Note that the currents provided by this HFR system have been used to study the sardine recruitment in the area ([Sciascia et al., 2018](#)), hence further demonstrating the relevance of such an observing system in this particular location.

In the Gulf of Trieste, only two sites (one in Italy, one in Slovenia) are available, with long periods of failure to function. The Gulf of Naples, equipped with 3 antenna sites, is a complex area with several islands and an irregular coastline (Fig. 4). Finally, the HFR system in the northeast of Gran Canaria, managed by the Canary Islands Oceanic Platform (PLOCAN, <https://www.plocan.eu>) was tested as an example of near real-time data processing (Section 5).

Figure 4 | Examples of radials in the Gulf of Naples and the Gulf of Trieste.

2 Interpolation method

Specific methods were previously designed and applied to combine radial velocities into a gridded field of total velocities (e.g. [Lekien, 2004](#); [Kim et al., 2007, 2008](#); [Fredj et al., 2016](#)). One of the most frequently employed method is the *Open-Boundary Modal Analysis* (OMA, [Kaplan and Lekien, 2007](#)).

In this report we will use a variational method called DIVAnd, described in the next Section. Comparisons between DIVAnd and OMA have been performed in [Barth et al. \(2021\)](#). In the case of the Ibiza Channel, the DIVAnd method, compares favorably to the OMA results, especially when several time instances are considered simultaneously for the interpolation.

Such comparisons between methods are not performed in the present work, as we consider that the DIVA framework has already been tested and validated in a variety of situations.

2.1 DIVAnd analysis tool

The analysis technique employed is called DIVAnd, which stands for n-dimensional Data Interpolating Variational Analysis. The software tool has been designed to perform spatial analysis in a n-dimensional domain (longitude, latitude, time, depth, ...) and doing so, generate a set of gridded fields of the variables of interest, based on sparse measurements.

Strictly speaking, DIVAnd does not perform pure interpolation, but rather *approximation* or *analysis*, meaning that the gridded field does not have to contain all the data points. To do so, it minimises a cost function that takes into account various constraints (e.g., [Troupin et al., 2010, 2012](#); [Beckers et al., 2014](#); [Barth et al., 2014](#)):

The observations: the analysis is expected to be relatively close the observations. However, it is not imposed to have an analysis that exactly goes through all the observations, as these are affected by different types of error: instrumental, representativity, synopticity (e.g. [Rixen et al., 2001](#)). This constraint is implemented in the cost function as a term penalizing the misfit between the observations and the field value at the same locations.

The regularity of the reconstructed field: a physical field (temperature, salinity for example) is expected to display reasonable gradients and irregularities in order to be considered as realistic at the scale of interest. This constraint is implemented in the cost function as a term penalizing the gradient and the Laplacian of the resulting field.

In this extension of DIVAnd specific to high-frequency radar, new physical constraints relevant to a velocity fields were added, namely:

boundary conditions: it ensures that the velocity component perpendicular to a physical obstacle, the coast in this case, is close to zero;

divergence: the divergence of the flow is also expected to be weak;

influence of the Coriolis force: it ensure that the velocity at given time is similar to the velocity at a previous and next time instance.

2.2 DIVAnd code

The DIVAnd code, written in the Julia language (Bezanson et al., 2017), is available from GitHub at <https://github.com/gher-ulg/DIVAnd.jl>. It has been previously applied to in situ observations (temperature, salinity, nutrient concentration) in the frame of SeaDataCloud project (<http://seadatanet.org/>), EMODnet Chemistry (<http://emodnet-chemistry.eu/>) and Biology lots (<https://www.emodnet-biology.eu/>).

The DIVAnd tool is well-adapted to perform the interpolation of radial HFR velocities since it allows one to work on large data sets without needing a super-computer, while it also offers the possibility to seamlessly add other constraints on the analysed field.

The implementation of specific constraints on the velocity in the cost function constitutes an innovative contribution of the present work. The decision to work on the radial velocities instead of the total velocities, obtained by combining the velocities from various radar stations, is expected to lead to a better spatial coverage and to provide total currents even at the edges of the antennas coverage.

3 Implementation of DIVAnd

3.1 Choice of the output grid

The spatial resolution of the output grid is set to be the similar to the spatial resolution of the observation, which means it may depend on the region of interest. The temporal resolution is also set according to the frequency of the radial velocity data. In most of the case, data are provided with a resolution of one hour, whereas regions are updated every 30 minutes.

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta x &= 0.02^\circ \\ \Delta y &= 0.02^\circ \\ \Delta t &= 3600 \text{ s}\end{aligned}$$

Figure 5 shows a 0.02° by 0.02° grid in the Gulf of Manfredonia. The extension of the final grid is selected according to the coverage of the radials. Note that that one of the four available antennas, MANF, is located on a dock offshore, which may give the impression that it is in the sea.

3.2 Preparation of the bathymetry

A local bathymetry is required to create a land-sea mask, since the interpolation method takes into account the physical boundaries. In order to get a mask with a sufficiently high spatial resolution, the bathymetry is extracted from the EMODnet Bathymetry portal (<https://portal.emodnet-bathymetry.eu/>) for the region of interest. The downloaded file ("ESRI ASCII") is then transformed into netCDF so it can be directly ingested by DIVAnd. Examples of obtained bathymetries are shown in Fig. 6.

The land-sea mask consists of a matrix filled with 1's (ocean/sea grid points) and 0's (for land grid points). It is directly obtained from the bathymetry (Fig. 7), and can be edited for instance to remove isolated sea grid points located on land.

Figure 5 | Spatial grid for the combined current field. The grid is theoretical as no data are almost never available close to the coast, far from the radar sites and also along the line joining the 2 sites.

Figure 6 | Example of high-resolution bathymetries extracted from the EMODnet Bathymetry portal.

Figure 7 | Land-sea mask constructed from the bathymetry. The interpolation is only performed on the "sea" points, and is also used for the boundary condition constraint.

3.3 Analysis parameters

The main analysis parameters to determine are:

1. the spatial correlation length L_x , assuming that the observed field is isotropic. L_x has to be of the same order of magnitude as Δx , so we will start with a first-guess of 5 km.
2. the temporal correlation length L_t , which provides an information on the time over which the spatial fields are correlated in time.
3. the noise-to-signal ratio ε^2 . This parameters is not easy to evaluate direction, hence a cross-validation approach will be followed (Section 3.5).
4. the relative importance of the additional constraints: boundary condition (ε_{bc}^2), divergence (ε_{div}^2) and Coriolis force (ε_{cor}^2).

The parameter selection is rather complex as there are a large number of possible combinations. The cross-validation technique (Section 3.5) which consists of setting apart some of the observations, extracting the velocity field at those locations, and then computing the difference between the two, could help us find the optimal set of values.

Nevertheless, applying the method to different dates or using a different site can provide different *optimal* combinations of parameters. This is why we also performed a sensitivity analysis (Section 3.4), in order to show how the results change when one or another analysis parameter is modified.

3.4 Sensitivity analysis

The goal of this set of analysis is to illustrate the effect of each analysis parameter on the gridded field by performing tests with a wide range of values.

3.4.1 Correlation length

The tested values are 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2 and 5°, with a fixed noise-to-signal ratio $\varepsilon^2 = 1.0$ (Fig. 8). Small values of L lead to the presence of smaller-scale features, while large values create a more uniform velocity field. It is worth noting that changing the L value, let us say from 0.1° to 0.01°, has almost no effect on the present structures. This also

means that, when optimizing the analysis parameters, there is no unique value of a given parameter, but rather a range of values that will generate similar analysis fields.

3.4.2 Noise-to-signal ration

The tested values for ε^2 are 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1., 10., 100. The correlation length is kept constant (0.1°) while the other constrains are not activated (Fig. 9).

A low noise-to-signal ratio means that the signal of the observation is strong in the analysis, hence many small-scale features appear in the velocity field. Oppositely, the analysis with a large ε^2 value display a more uniform field. Similarly to the previous Section about the correlation length, we see here that multiplying ε^2 by 10 almost does not affect the velocity field.

3.4.3 Relative importance of the boundary condition constraint

The role of this constraint is to ensure that currents do not flow into the coastline. The tested values for ε_{bc}^2 are: 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1., 10., 100. The correlation length ($L = 0.1^\circ$) and the noise-to-signal ratio ($\varepsilon^2 = 1.0$) are kept constant, while the divergence constraint is not activated (Fig. 10).

The set of analysis presented in Fig. 10 shows that the influence of the boundary condition constraint is limited, even for the wide range of values tested. The region most affected by this constraint is located north of the Gargano Promontory, where only the northernmost antenna, VIES, provides measurements.

3.4.4 Relative importance of the divergence constraint

The role of the divergence constraint is to reduce non-physical flow structures by penalizing the horizontal divergence of the flow. The tested values for ε_{div}^2 are 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1., 10., 100. The correlation length is kept constant (0.1°) while the boundary constraint is not activated (Fig. 11).

The conclusions from this set of tests is similar to the previous Section: changing ε_{div}^2 does not affect significantly the results of the interpolation for the range of values tested.

3.5 Cross-validation

In order to determine the best set of parameters, a cross-validation is performed as follows:

1. The radial velocities from one of the four antennas (MATT in this case) are discarded.
2. The velocity field is reconstructed with DIVAnd, using the radial velocities from the 3 remaining sites.
3. The velocity field is extracted (re-interpolated) at the locations of the discarded measurements and projected onto the radial direction.
4. The RMS difference between the original (discarded) radial and the radial obtained in the previous step is computed.

The procedure is then repeated for different combinations of the analysis parameters, and the combination leading to the lowest RMS difference is assumed to be the optimal one. The tested values are:

Horizontal correlation length (L) : 0.01°, 0.05°, 0.1°, 0.5°, 1.0°, 2.0° and 5.0°.

Noise-to-signal ratio: 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1. and 5.

Relative importance of boundary constraint: 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1. and 5.

Relative importance of divergence constraint: 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1. and 5.

The test is applied on different dates in order to see if the optimal combination of parameters remains the same. The results tend to show that it is not the case: it is not easily possible to identify a unique combination. The analysis were then performed with a set of parameters based on the conclusions of the sensitivity analysis (Section 3.4).

Figure 8 | Sensitivity analysis for the correlation length.

Figure 9 | Sensitivity analysis for the noise-to-signal ratio.

Figure 10 | Sensitivity analysis for the boundary condition constraint.

Figure 11 | Sensitivity analysis for the divergence constraint.

3.6 Summary: description of the procedure

- 1 Specify the region of interest (rectangular bounding box, in the form `lonmin`, `lonmax`, `latmin`, `latmax`), based on the coverage of the different radials.
- 2 Prepare a high-resolution bathymetry for the region (function `emodnet2nc`).
- 3 Set the period of interest (initial and final dates).
- 4 Set the analysis parameters: correlation length (lon, lat and possibly time), noise-to-signal ratio, relative importance of the constraint (divergence, boundary, Coriolis).
- 5 Specify the metadata of the netCDF files (function `prepare_results_nc`).
- 6 Run the interpolation.
- 7 Write the netCDF files.

The script `interp-velocity-manfredonia-run.jl` implements the different steps of the procedure. Analysis can be performed to other regions with only a few adaptations.

4 Results

The first version (V1) of the gridded products has been prepared with the following parameters:

$$\begin{aligned}
 L &= 0.1 \\
 \varepsilon^2 &= 1. \\
 \varepsilon_{bc}^2 &= 1. \\
 \varepsilon_{div}^2 &= 0.01
 \end{aligned}$$

4.1 Availability

The results are available from <https://dox.ulg.ac.be/index.php/s/3nfdYzjR644Qah8>. The structure of the directories is as follow:

data: contains auxiliary data files that can be used for the analysis, in particular the high-resolution bathymetries used to prepare the land-sea mask (Section 3.2).

results: contains the results (one folder by region); for each region, different versions of the product can exist, depending on the constraints applied for the analysis.

test-data: data files used for unit testing of the code.

4.2 Output format

The results are written in netCDF-4 files (Rew and Davis, 1990). One file is created by month, and is approximately 45M. The format (header and variable metadata) is based on existing files for other gridded HF radar products in the European Seas (e.g. Corgnati et al., 2018; Mantovani et al., 2020). For the variables, the Climate and Forecast (CF) conventions were followed.

In order to increase the *reproducibility*, the version numbers of the tools are added in the netCDF header (entries `In` addition, a netCDF *group*, containing the analysis parameters is also created in each file. In this group, one finds the following variables:

- Correlation length along x-direction,
- Correlation length along y-direction,
- Temporal correlation length,
- Noise-to-signal ratio,

- Relative error variance of the boundary constraints,
- Relative error variance of the divergence constraints,
- Relative error variance of the Coriolis constraint.

4.3 Observed features

The main oceanographic feature in the Gulf of Manfredonia is the *West Adriatic Current* (WAC), which flows southeast along the Italian coast (e.g. Orlić et al., 1992; Cushman-Roisin et al., 2001; Poulain, 2001). It is a buoyant coastal current driven by the Po River (northern Adriatic Sea). The WAC is also influenced by the wind: it is strengthened by the northwesterly winds, most common in summer (Magaldi et al., 2009; Pasarić et al., 2009). The WAC is clearly visible in monthly averaged fields (Fig. 12).

Figure 12 | Monthly averaged fields in February, May, August and November 2014.

Smaller-scale features, such as eddies and filaments, also take place in the area (Burrage et al., 2009).

Figure 13 | *Drifter trajectories in the Ibiza Channel.*

4.4 Validation

The validation of the results can be performed in various ways but strongly depends on the availability of other data sources in the area of interest, in particular instruments capable of providing information on the surface currents, for instance surface drifting buoys or a current-meter on a mooring.

The collection of surface drifters deployed in the Mediterranean Sea and in particular in the Adriatic Sea provided a view of the general circulation in the region (e.g., Poulain, 2001; Poulain et al., 2013), but the lack of drifters in coastal region make their use difficult for a validation.

An exception occur when specific validation experiments are carried out. This was the case in the Ibiza Channel in September-October 2014, where 11 drifters from different manufacturers were deployed in 4 locations inside the area covered by the HF radar system managed by SOCIB (Fig. 13, Lana et al., 2015, 2016). Unfortunately the drifters quickly left the zone covered by the HFR, thus only providing a limited data set for the validation, exploited in Barth et al. (2021).

Another possibility consists to derive the velocity indirectly, from consecutive images obtained by remote-sensing, see for example Delandmeter et al. (2017). The inconvenient of such a method is that it requires images with a sufficient spatial resolution combined with a good coverage (i.e., absence of clouds). In the Adriatic Sea, Notarstefano et al. (2008) estimated surface currents using sequential infrared satellite images (sea surface temperature). The inconvenient of the method is that it does not allow one to know if the changes in sea surface temperature can be attributed to advection or to other processes (upwelling for example).

4.4.1 External dataset: chlorophyll concentration

Here for the validation, satellite images of chlorophyll concentration have been used. The presence of clouds constitutes an obstacle for the validation: the quality of the images strongly changes from one day to the next (Fig. 14). higher coastal values, then offshore transport more evidenced in the form of filaments

We selected images that had a good spatial coverage and displayed particular features, such as filaments of higher concentration of chlorophyll, extending offshore (Fig. 15). On August 12, 2014, we can observe a filament developing north-eastward from the extremity of the Cape (Fig. 15a). The velocity field reconstructed with DIVAnd displays northward current that detaches from the Cape and flow northeastward (Fig. 15b), compatible with the chlorophyll concentration observation. On September 9, 2014, a zone of higher chlorophyll concentration develops southeastward from the Cape (Fig. 15c), in agreement with the velocity field obtained with DIVAnd (Fig. 15d).

5 Near real-time application: Gran Canaria

In order to demonstrate the application of the method to another region, we processed the near real-time data covering the northeast of Gran Canaria (Canary Islands, Fig. 16).

5.1 Adaptations to the scripts

Some adaptations to the scripts are required in order to perform the calculations in another domain:

1. Definition of the period and the domain of interest (bounding box).

Figure 14 | Temporal and spatial coverage of the chlorophyll concentration satellite images for 2014.

2. List of the site names (needed for the data reading).
3. Extraction of the regional bathymetry.
4. Modification of the analysis parameters and the spatial resolution (optional).
5. Modification of the functions that create the lists of URLs to access the data. Note that it would not be trivial to have a generic function that could deal with all the different regions, due to the way the THREDDS is structured. Yet, adapting the function is rather straightforward.
6. Reading of the data: the netCDF files have not exactly the same format in all the situations. For example, the coordinates of the radar sites can appear as a global attribute (Origin) and can be written as variables (SLTR, SLNR, SLTT, SLNT). The velocity and the direction have also different variable names, but this can be easily overcome by using the *standard names* to find the correct variable, whatever its name. Finally, we can also mention that in some files, the main variables depend on the time, longitude and latitude coordinates, while in other files the same variables depend on time, longitude, latitude and depth.

All in all, adapting the scripts to create gridded velocity fields from the radial velocities available on the THREDDS server is not a time-consuming task, hence the creation of new products can be considered.

5.2 Surface current of Gran Canaria

In this section we will briefly show some results corresponding to December 2021 (Fig. 18). The validation of this product is not easy due to the scarcity of other source of data in the area: the only platform available at the time of the study is a tide gauge located in the harbour of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (<https://map.emodnet-physics.eu/platformpage/?platformid=8711>).

We performed a comparison between our results and the IBI model (*Atlantic-iberian Biscay Irish- Ocean Physics Analysis And Forecast*, product IBI_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_005_001), provided by CMEMS (Fig. 17). On December 24, 2021, a cyclonic circulation pattern is present in both fields, though its position slightly differs. The order of magnitude of the velocity are also in agreement, with maximal values close to 0.3 m/s. On December 28, 2021, the flow is mostly northwestward, but the magnitude of the velocity obtained with DIVAnd is lower near the coast.

6 Discussion

In this report we have presented the results of the spatio-temporal interpolation of radial velocities for the construction of gridded, surface velocity fields. While the present report focuses mainly on the Gulf of Manfredonia (east coast of Italy), the procedure (Sec. 3.6) and the tools designed for the gridding are sufficiently general to be easily adapted for other regions (example of the Gulf of Naples in Fig. 19).

The use of time-related parameters (temporal correlation length and Coriolis constraint) can be necessary in situations when only 2 radar sites are available, for instance in the Gulf of Trieste.

Figure 15 | Validation of surface current by comparison with chlorophyll concentration from satellite.

Radial velocities in the Gran Canaria region
on 2021-12-23 20:00:00

Figure 16 | Radial velocities northeast of the island of Gran Canaria. The two sites are located in the harbor of Las Palmas of Gran Canaria (MAND) and in the harbor of Taliarte (TALI).

The validation of the results is often a difficult task, due to the lack of independent measurements (in situ platform for example) to perform the comparison. Here we employed satellite images and numerical model outputs to validate qualitatively our results.

Figure 17 | Comparison of the reconstructed velocity fields with DIVAnd (left) and the velocity from the IBI model (right).

Figure 18 | Radials and reconstructed velocity field northeast of Gran Canaria island.

Figure 19 | Example of reconstructed velocity field in the Gulf of Naples.

Code and data availability

The DIVAnd code is made available through GitHub at <https://gitlab.uliege.be/gher/diva-emodnetphysics>.

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This project took advantage of netCDF software developed by UCAR/Unidata (<http://doi.org/10.5065/D6H70CW6>).

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